

ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY, SPEAKING CONFIDENCE AND DIGITAL EXPOSURE: IMPLICATIONS ON ENGLISH SPEAKING FLUENCY

Dawn Princess B. Carciller, Kriscentti Exzur P. Barcelona, Ph.D.,

Lourdes College Inc., Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15529243>

ABSTRACT

English speaking fluency is crucial for academic and professional success in multilingual contexts, yet many students in Philippine public schools struggle to achieve it. This study investigated the influence of language proficiency, speaking confidence, and digital exposure on the speaking fluency of Grade 8 students in Philippine public schools in Cagayan de Oro City, Northern Mindanao, Philippines. A descriptive-correlational design was used, and data were collected from 245 students across two schools through a stratified random sampling to ensure representation from different student groups. Language proficiency was assessed with a researcher-made multiple-choice test. Speaking confidence and digital engagement were measured using questionnaires, gathering self-reported data on these constructs. Speaking performance was evaluated an impromptu speech presentation using a rubric to ensure consistent and objective scoring. Results showed Fair overall language proficiency, with good comprehension, Moderate speaking confidence with classroom anxiety, and Moderate-to-Low digital exposure, indicating limited use of advanced digital tools for language learning. Speaking fluency was generally Fair, with better performance in automaticity than coherence/accuracy. Regression analysis indicated that language proficiency and digital exposure significantly influenced speaking fluency, while speaking confidence did not. The model explained a small portion of the variance in speaking fluency. These findings suggest that educators may balance instruction by focusing on authentic content to improve comprehension, creating low-anxiety environments to enhance confidence, explicitly teaching discourse organization and grammar, and guiding digital tool use. Future research could explore motivation, learning strategies, and out-of-classroom speaking opportunities.

Keywords: *English speaking fluency, English language proficiency, speaking confidence, digital exposure, ESL learners, Philippine education*

INTRODUCTION

English speaking fluency, the ability to communicate easily and effectively, is a fundamental aspect of language learning, depending on language proficiency, confidence, and digital exposure (Muñoz-Ocampo, 2022). Research has highlighted the significance of linguistic variables like vocabulary and grammar in developing speaking skills (Lestari et al., 2019), while confidence, as an emotional factor, boosts learners' motivation in speaking activities (Hidayat et al., 2020). Digital exposure, encompassing technology and digital tool usage, has become a vital element impacting English speaking fluency, offering students practical opportunities to apply their language knowledge (Rahman et al., 2021).

Dincer and Dariyemez (2020) noted that prior linguistic experience and the learning environment significantly influence students' perceptions of their confidence and motivation. Bucay and Rosil (2024) found a positive correlation between academic motivation and second language fluency, indicating that more motivated individuals achieve higher fluency levels. Similarly, Han et al. (2020) analyzed the relationship between utterance fluency measures and observed fluency ratings, emphasizing the multifaceted nature of excellent delivery. Fauzi et al. (2021) discussed cognitive, linguistic, and affective factors affecting speaking fluency.

Recent studies have also underscored the role of digital exposure. Mulyani and Wibisono (2021) demonstrated how digital platforms can foster learners' speaking skills by providing real-world communication experiences. Likewise, Lee and Chen (2022) observed that digital immersion environments, such as online learning settings, enhance learners' fluency and confidence by simulating authentic language use scenarios.

In the Philippine public school system, English is a second language and a medium of instruction in various subjects. Despite this emphasis, many students still struggle with speaking fluency. Consequently, this study focuses on Grade 8 learners in Philippine public schools, a crucial stage where developing speaking fluency can significantly impact their future academic and professional paths.

This study aims to provide valuable insights into effective teaching practices for improving students' speaking by examining the interconnected factors of language proficiency, confidence, and digital exposure. By gaining a deeper understanding of these factors and their contribution to speaking fluency, this research intends to inform the development of strategies to address the challenges learners face in expressing themselves fluently. The findings are expected to serve as a guide for teachers in implementing strategies that enhance language proficiency while making the learning process more engaging and motivating for students. Given the study's context within Philippine public schools, its

recommendations will be tailored to improve the quality of English language teaching in the country.

Despite growing research on the determinants of speaking fluency, few studies have specifically concentrated on the public-school setting in the Philippines (Muñoz Ocampo, 2022; Lestari et al., 2019; Hidayat et al., 2020). The present study seeks to fill this void by investigating the interplay of language proficiency, confidence, and digital exposure among Grade 8 learners in Philippine public schools. Furthermore, this research aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4, which emphasizes the urgency of achieving quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all (United Nations, 2015). The findings of this study will contribute to the development of effective teaching methods and strategies aimed at promoting quality education and lifelong learning opportunities within the Philippine public school system.

Ultimately, this study bridges the research gap concerning the effects of language proficiency, confidence, and digital exposure on the speaking fluency of Grade 8 learners in Philippine public schools. By offering context-specific insights and recommendations, this research aims to contribute to the attainment of SDG 4 and the enhancement of English language education in the Philippines.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study assumes that Grade 8 Learners' speaking fluency is influenced by their language proficiency, speaking confidence, and digital exposure.

The research is based on three theoretical frameworks: Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985), Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1997) and Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of Learning (1978).

Stephen Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1981) has significantly changed the second language acquisition process. He suggested that people learn most effectively when exposed to input in a language just beyond their current grasp. Krashen (1981) argues that for language acquisition to occur, the input must be comprehensible, meaningful, relevant, and contextualized to the learner's experiences. Moreover, he emphasizes that anxiety plays a crucial role in language learning. This hypothesis applies well to variables of language proficiency and digital exposure. Authentic digital materials expose learners to meaningful input, and digital tools provide a safe space to practice, reducing anxiety and enhancing language acquisition.

Albert Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1997) offers a psychological perspective on language learning, focusing on how a learner's belief in their ability to perform specific tasks affects their success. Bandura (1997) identified four primary sources of self-efficacy: mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and emotional states. In speaking fluency, students with high self-efficacy are more likely to participate and persist.

The Sociocultural Theory of Lev Vygotsky (1978) undergirds the social and cultural aspects of learning. Vygotsky's theory centralizes the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) and the role of a more knowledgeable other (MKO) in learning. In language learning, digital tools can serve as MKOs, providing scaffolding and support. The theory also emphasizes the importance of social interaction and collaboration in language development.

Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1981), Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory (1997), and Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978) together provide a robust theoretical framework for understanding the interplay of language proficiency, speaking confidence, and digital exposure in influencing speaking fluency.

Research Questions

This study will determine the influence of English language proficiency, speaking confidence and digital exposure on English speaking fluency.

Specifically, this study will answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the participants' English language proficiency considering:
 - 1.1 Vocabulary;
 - 1.2 Grammar; and
 - 1.3 Comprehension?
2. What are the participants' level of speaking confidence?
What is the participants' extent of digital exposure in terms of:
 - 3.1 Interaction with digital media in English
 - 3.2 Use of AI language tools and online videos
3. What is the level of the participants' English speaking fluency in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 4.1 Automaticity
 - 4.2 Coherence and cohesion
 - 4.3 Accuracy?
5. Do the participants' level of English language proficiency, speaking confidence and digital exposure influence their English speaking fluency?

Review of Related Literature and Studies

The influence of language proficiency of students' speaking fluency skills. Language proficiency is viewed as the capacity to effectively use language across contexts, encompassing linguistic and communicative competencies. Recent studies have refined our understanding of this, with Montrul (2021) proposing a multi-componential model that includes vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension, highlighting the interconnectedness of these elements. Vocabulary, a key component, is the words one knows and uses for communication; research indicates a strong positive relationship between vocabulary size and language proficiency (Schmitt, 2019; Dóczy & Kormos, 2021). Grammar, the rules of

sentence structure and language usage, is crucial for coherent communication (Biber et al., 2020). Recent work has emphasized grammar's role in constructing well-formed sentences and conveying meaning accurately (Larsen-Freeman, 2021; Ellis, 2022). Comprehension, the ability to understand language, is fundamental for meaningful interaction (Vandergrift & Goh, 2019). Studies continue to explore the link between comprehension and language proficiency (Grabe & Stoller, 2022; Koda, 2023; Grabe, 2021).

Speaking confidence, a psychological factor, significantly impacts a learner's communication. Cheng and Yang (2019) analyzed how confidence predicts language learning behavior, with confident speakers more likely to engage in communicative tasks. Bakar et al. (2021) defined speaking confidence as the belief in one's ability to perform speaking tasks successfully, influencing language proficiency. MacIntyre and Gregersen (2021) characterized speaking confidence as a psychological trait affecting cognitive and emotional aspects of language learning.

Digital exposure, the extent of interaction with digital tools and media in the target language, is a critical factor in modern language acquisition. Yang (2020) notes that digital exposure facilitates language learning through digital content. This exposure includes interaction with digital media like social media (Lambert and Zhang, 2022), AI language tools (Saito and Plonsky, 2023), and online videos (Webb, 2021). Research indicates that digital media enhances vocabulary acquisition, writing competence, and communicative competence (Rodriguez-Escobar et al., 2023). AI language tools offer personalized practice and feedback (Saito and Plonsky, 2023), while online videos provide multimodal input and cultural insights (Chen et al., 2024).

English Speaking fluency, the ability to express oneself smoothly, is a key aspect of language proficiency (Segalowitz, 2022). It comprises sub-variables like automaticity (Gass and Selinker, 2019; Lambert and Zhang, 2022; Saito and Plonsky, 2023), coherence and cohesion (Hyland, 2021; McCarthy, 2021), and accuracy (Ellis, 2020; Foster & Skehan, 2021)

Significance of the Study

This study holds implications for various stakeholders in English language education. The findings will enhance understanding of how language proficiency, speaking confidence, and digital exposure interact to influence learners' speaking fluency. Specifically, the research benefits students by providing insights into the factors that enhance speaking fluency, thereby guiding their learning strategies and encouraging the use of targeted practice and digital tools. It informs English teachers by offering practical insights for integrating instructional strategies that foster students' speaking confidence, language proficiency, and effective use of digital resources. The study also guides school administrators by highlighting the importance of creating supportive learning environments and informing policies that promote speaking fluency through digital tools and confidence-building activities. Furthermore, this research contributes to future research on language acquisition by providing a foundation for further exploration of how

language proficiency, speaking confidence can be optimized to improve speaking fluency. In essence, this study addresses a crucial gap in understanding the interplay of these factors, offering both theoretical contributions to the field of language acquisition and practical guidance for improving English language instruction and learning outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design with a quantitative approach to investigate the relationships among English language proficiency, speaking confidence, digital exposure, and speaking fluency. This design, common in establishing variable relationships (Cagalitan et al., 2023), utilizes structured data collection like questionnaires and performance assessments to analyze how beliefs and abilities affect performance (Rincon et al., 2020). The study used a researcher-developed language proficiency test, an adapted speaking confidence questionnaire (potentially drawing insights from Shen & Chiu, 2019), a structured digital exposure survey (Zhang et al., 2021), and oral assessments to measure speaking fluency. Correlation analysis was used to determine the strength and direction of the relationships between these factors, aiming to understand how proficiency, confidence, and digital exposure relate to spoken output. The findings were intended to provide detailed insights into students' linguistic performance and the influences on it, informing instructional strategies.

The participants were 245 Grade 8 students enrolled in two public junior high schools in Cagayan de Oro City, Philippines, during the 2024-2025 academic year. Stratified random sampling was used to select participants from the West I district, regardless of gender or English proficiency. The primary criterion for inclusion was the students' speaking fluency in oral recitations.

The study utilized three main instruments for data collection. First, English language proficiency was assessed using a researcher-made multiple-choice test evaluating vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension, tailored to the local context and curriculum. Second, two questionnaires were administered: one adapted to assess speaking confidence (Shen & Chiu, 2019) and another to determine the extent of digital exposure (Zhang et al., 2020). Finally, speaking fluency was evaluated through an impromptu speech presentation assessed by a rubric measuring automaticity, coherence and cohesion, and accuracy. Data was collected at the beginning and end of the fourth quarter of the school year to identify any changes over time.

The questionnaires and rubrics underwent validation by field experts and panel members who assessed content and relevance. Following their suggestions, the instruments were pilot-tested on a separate group. The questionnaire demonstrated high reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of .862, which is considered acceptable (Alkhadim, 2022). Other data collection aspects, including digital exposure, also showed acceptable to excellent reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from .747 to .903.

Language proficiency was measured by combining scores from vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension, with overall proficiency levels categorized (e.g., Outstanding, Very Good). Speaking confidence was assessed using a Likert-type scale, with scores corresponding to different confidence levels (e.g., Very Confident, Confident). Digital exposure was gauged by classifying scores from a technology use questionnaire into levels like Very High and High. Finally, speaking fluency was evaluated based on the impromptu speech, with scores aligned to fluency level descriptions (e.g., Very Good Fluency, Average Fluency).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the level of the participants' language proficiency considering: vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension?

Table 1 summarizes the language proficiency of the participants across vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension. The overall mean score of 8.50 ($SD = 2.63$), rated as "Fair," shows that while students have some language skills, they need improvement in most areas. Looking at specific scores, vocabulary averaged 8.09 ($SD = 3.08$), grammar 7.73 ($SD = 2.79$), and comprehension 9.69 ($SD = 4.45$), with the different standard deviations showing that students vary in how well they perform. These findings provide important insights for language teaching. The "Fair" scores in vocabulary and grammar indicate that many students have trouble with these basic language parts. This makes it hard for them to communicate well in school and social situations. Students did better in comprehension ("Good") than in vocabulary and grammar, showing that understanding language comes more easily than producing it. However, the high standard deviation in comprehension ($SD = 4.45$) reveals big differences between students, meaning teachers need to adjust their methods for different learning needs.

Table 1
Summary Table of the Participants' Language Proficiency

Dimensions of English Language Proficiency	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Vocabulary	8.09	Fair	3.08
Grammar	7.73	Fair	2.79
Comprehension	9.69	Good	4.45
Overall Language Proficiency	8.50	Fair	2.63

The vocabulary score ($M = 8.09$, "Fair") indicates that students can use and understand some words, but their word knowledge is still limited. This affects how well they can speak and write. Nation (2020) emphasized that good vocabulary knowledge is important for effective language use. A strong vocabulary helps students communicate more clearly and smoothly, so there's a need for better vocabulary teaching that covers both more words and deeper understanding of how to use them.

The grammar score of 7.73, also rated as "Fair," demonstrates that while students know some grammar rules, they often make mistakes that affect their ability to make complex sentences correctly. Ellis (2020) found that even though direct grammar teaching is important, students often have trouble using this knowledge when actually speaking or writing. These results point to a need for grammar teaching that not only covers the rules but also helps students apply them in real communication.

The emphasis on comprehension as a core receptive skill in this discussion aligns directly with the perspective of Vandergrift and Goh (2019), who underscore its fundamental role in effective communication. Their assertion that strong comprehension abilities form the basis for meaningful interaction is supported by the study's implication that better comprehension leads to improved language production. The understanding and interpretation of both spoken and written language, as highlighted by Vandergrift and Goh, directly facilitates appropriate responses in various communicative contexts observed in the learners' performance.

The effects of comprehension on overall language development, particularly its role in learning from lectures, understanding reading materials, and participating in discussions, resonate with the findings of Rost (2020). His emphasis on comprehension-based training enhancing both listening and reading skills, and more importantly, improving lexical and grammatical accuracy, provides a theoretical framework for the observed connection between comprehension and language production in this study.

From a practical teaching standpoint, the relatively better performance in comprehension compared to vocabulary and grammar in this study suggests a potential developmental pattern where receptive skills may precede productive ones. This observation highlights the importance of explicit comprehension-focused instruction, as supported by Ahn's (2020) finding that comprehension training significantly improves overall communicative competence, particularly in academic contexts. The need to strengthen both basic and advanced comprehension skills aligns with the pedagogical goal of enabling learners to construct more coherent and well-structured responses in both writing and speaking.

Therefore, the data from this study reinforce the crucial role of effective comprehension skills in overall language development. While the participants demonstrate generally good comprehension, the need for continuous improvement, especially among those with lower proficiency, underscores the necessity for language instruction to persistently focus on enhancing these abilities. A comprehensive approach that integrates comprehension with grammar and speaking practice is essential to further support learners in achieving higher levels of proficiency and fluency in their language use, building upon the foundational receptive skills as highlighted by the literature.

Research Question 2: What is the participants' level of speaking confidence?

Table 2 reveals the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' level of speaking confidence. The overall mean score is 2.62 ($SD = 0.65$), interpreted as

"Moderately Confident." This shows that most students feel somewhat comfortable when speaking but still face challenges in public speaking situations. This moderate confidence affects students' willingness to speak in class and their overall language development.

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Level of Speaking Confidence

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very Confident	0	0.00
3.51-4.50	Confident	18	7.35
2.51-3.50	Moderately Confident	115	46.94
1.51-2.50	Slightly Confident	103	42.04
1.00-1.50	Not at all Confident	9	3.67
Total		245	100.0
Overall Mean		2.62	
Interpretation		Moderately Confident	
SD		0.65	

Most participants (46.94%) fall in the *"Moderately Confident"* range, while 42.04 percent are *"Slightly Confident."* Only 7.35 percent reported being *"Confident,"* and 3.67 percent were *"Not at all Confident."* No students reached the *"Very Confident"* level. Fabriz et. al (2021) found that public speaking anxiety is common among language learners and affects their performance. The lack of highly confident students shows a problem that needs attention.

The highest-scoring indicators show that anxiety is a major barrier to speaking confidence. The items *"I feel nervous when speaking in front of my classmates"* ($M = 3.89$) received the highest score. The item was reversely scored, meaning students reported high anxiety in these situations.

The finding that students reported high levels of anxiety related to speaking tasks ($M = 3.52$) for *"I feel nervous when I have to speak in English"*) directly aligns with the research of Senaratne et al. (2022), who identified anxiety as a significant impediment to speaking confidence. Furthermore, Rost's (2020) observation that speaking anxiety intensifies when students are required to produce language spontaneously provides a framework for understanding the challenges these Grade 8 learners in Cagayan de Oro might face in impromptu speaking situations. The high anxiety levels reported in this study underscore the necessity, as suggested, for teachers to cultivate less stressful classroom environments and equip students with effective anxiety management strategies.

The high score for *"I am too hard on myself after giving a speech or presentation"* ($M = 3.41$) echoes the findings of Loew (2020), who noted that self-criticism often surpasses external feedback and exacerbates anxiety. This tendency among the participants highlights the need to assist students in developing more balanced self-assessment skills

and reframing mistakes as integral learning opportunities, rather than viewing them as failures.

The low scores for "I volunteer to give presentations in class" ($M = 2.24$) and "I am comfortable speaking in front of an audience of any size" ($M = 2.33$) are consistent with the explanations provided by Azam et al. (2020), who elucidated how avoidance of speaking opportunities creates a negative cycle of limited practice and sustained low confidence. This avoidance behavior among the students in this study emphasizes the importance of creating inclusive environments where all students are encouraged to participate.

Similarly, the low confidence reported in using gestures and body language ($M = 2.45$), maintaining eye contact ($M = 2.50$), and employing techniques like humor or storytelling ($M = 2.51$) underscores the significance of nonverbal communication in how speakers are perceived, as emphasized by Zhang and Ardabili (2019). The students' low scores in these areas indicate a clear need for explicit instruction and opportunities to practice these nonverbal skills within supportive classroom settings in Cagayan de Oro.

The mid-range scores for belief in improvement ("I believe that I can get better at public speaking by practicing more" and "I believe that my public speaking abilities can improve with effort," both $M = 2.82$) coupled with lower scores for actual practice ($M = 2.80$) and preparation ($M = 2.65$) illustrate a potential disconnect between students' beliefs and their actions. This gap aligns with the suggestion by Jansen et al. (2022) that students require specific preparation techniques and accountability measures to translate their beliefs into consistent practice.

Overall, the findings from this study strongly support the implementation of several teaching strategies to enhance speaking confidence. The need to create supportive speaking environments and ensure all students participate, rather than relying on volunteers, is consistent with the recommendations derived from the anxiety and avoidance findings. Furthermore, the necessity of teaching specific preparation and delivery techniques, as well as fostering a growth mindset about speaking, is reinforced by the literature on self-criticism and the belief-action gap. Finally, Marchiori's (2023) finding that positive feedback and supportive environments are crucial for building speaking confidence provides a guiding principle for educators in Cagayan de Oro to address the challenges identified in this study.

Research Question 3: What is the participants' extent of digital exposure in terms of:

- 3.1. Interaction with Digital Media in English; and**
- 3.2. Use of AI Language Tools and Online Videos?**

Table 3 illustrates a summary of the participants' digital exposure across two dimensions: interaction with digital media in English and use of AI language tools and online videos. The overall mean score is 2.54 ($SD = 0.61$), interpreted as "*Moderate*." This indicates that

students have some engagement with digital technologies for language learning, but their exposure is not extensive. This moderate level of digital engagement has important implications for language education in today's increasingly digital world.

Looking at the specific dimensions, "Interaction with Digital Media in English" scored slightly higher with a mean of 2.57 ($SD = 0.68$), interpreted as "Moderate," while "Use of AI Language Tools and Online Videos" scored lower at 2.50 ($SD = 0.71$), interpreted as "Low." This difference, though small, reveals that students are somewhat more comfortable engaging with general digital media in English than with specialized AI tools designed for language learning. Kapp et al. (2020) noted that while students are increasingly immersed in digital environments, their interaction is often casual or entertainment-focused rather than academic.

Table 3
Summary Table of the Participants' Digital Exposure

Dimensions of Digital Exposure	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Interaction with Digital Media in English	2.57	Moderate	0.68
Use of AI Language Tools and Online Videos	2.50	Low	0.71
Overall Digital Exposure	2.54	Moderate	0.61

Despite the relatively low scores for AI tool usage, classroom observations and student output sometimes contradict these self-reported figures. Some students appear to be using AI tools like grammar checkers and writing assistants more extensively than they report, as evidenced by the polished nature of certain submissions and the sudden improvement in language complexity in their work. Several possible explanations exist for this contradiction. Students may underreport their AI tool usage due to concerns about academic integrity or the perception that using such tools constitutes "cheating."

Additionally, students might be using these tools without fully recognizing them as AI-powered, such as autocorrect features or spelling suggestions that are now integrated into many applications.

The data's revelation that Grade 8 learners in Cagayan de Oro are not fully leveraging digital resources for language learning, despite being digital natives, and that their engagement leans towards passive or recreational use, underscores a critical issue in contemporary education. This observation highlights a missed opportunity, as meaningful interaction with English digital content offers authentic language exposure and practice beyond the confines of the classroom.

The particularly low engagement with AI language tools and online videos is noteworthy considering the rapid advancement and increasing accessibility of these technologies. The potential of tools like ChatGPT, Grammarly, and YouTube for personalized language practice appears to be largely untapped by these students. This underutilization aligns with the observations of Ravshanovna (2024), who noted that without structured guidance

and integration into formal instruction, the potential of digital tools for language acquisition remains unrealized. This finding from the current study reinforces the idea that mere access to technology is insufficient; explicit instruction on effective usage for language development is crucial.

These findings from the Grade 8 learners in Cagayan de Oro strongly suggest a need for a more intentional and integrated approach to digital literacy education within language programs. Educational institutions should consider implementing structured strategies to introduce students to a diverse range of digital tools and platforms, providing clear guidance on their effective use for language learning, as opposed to mere entertainment.

The proposed strategies, such as classroom activities incorporating digital media analysis, assignments requiring the use of AI writing assistants with reflective feedback, and collaborative projects leveraging online video creation, offer concrete examples of how to bridge this gap and foster more purposeful digital engagement for language acquisition, aligning with the call for structured integration highlighted in the literature.

Research Question 4: What is the level of the participants' English speaking fluency in terms of the following dimensions:

- 4.1. Automaticity,**
- 4.2. Coherence and Cohesion; and**
- 4.3. Accuracy?**

Table 4 provides a summary of the participants' overall speaking fluency across three key dimensions: automaticity, coherence and cohesion, and accuracy. The overall mean score of 2.15 ($SD = 0.64$), interpreted as "*Fair Fluency*," shows that while learners are somewhat capable of expressing themselves in English, there are noticeable gaps in fluency that need attention. This moderate rating indicates that students can engage in conversation but often do so with hesitation, disorganized thoughts, or frequent errors.

Data related to the three dimensions reveal that automaticity scored the highest with a mean of 2.46 ($SD = 0.78$), still within the "*Fair Fluency*" range. This indicates that students are beginning to speak more spontaneously and with fewer pauses, which is a good foundation for communication. Students appear to be developing some ability to produce language in real-time, though they likely still experience hesitations when trying to express more complex ideas. This relative strength in automaticity provides a base upon which other aspects of fluency can be built.

The finding that coherence and cohesion scored 2.06 ($SD = 0.62$), placing it in the "*Fair Fluency*" category, aligns with Morales' (2021) observation that students often rely on memorized phrases and struggle with spontaneous elaboration, leading to breakdowns in coherence. The study's indication that learners can express simple relationships and maintain focus in short exchanges but falter in extended discourse supports the idea that developing the ability to logically organize complex ideas in spoken language is a significant hurdle for these Grade 8 learners in Cagayan de Oro.

The lowest mean score of 1.92 ($SD = 0.73$) in accuracy, categorized as "Poor Fluency," is consistent with the findings of Lemana II (2022). The research highlights that Filipino ESL learners frequently rely on simple grammatical structures and are prone to errors, particularly in spontaneous speech. This reinforces the conclusion that grammatical accuracy represents the most substantial challenge in the speaking fluency of the participants in this study.

Table 4
Summary Table of the Participants' Speaking Fluency

Dimensions of English Speaking Fluency	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Automaticity	2.46	Fair Fluency	0.78
Coherence and Cohesion	2.06	Fair Fluency	0.62
Accuracy	1.92	Poor Fluency	0.73
Overall Speaking Fluency	2.15	Fair Fluency	0.64

The lowest mean score of 1.92 ($SD = 0.73$) in accuracy, categorized as "Poor Fluency," is consistent with the findings of Lemana II (2022). The research highlights that Filipino ESL learners frequently rely on simple grammatical structures and are prone to errors, particularly in spontaneous speech. This reinforces the conclusion that grammatical accuracy represents the most substantial challenge in the speaking fluency of the participants in this study.

The pattern observed across the three dimensions of speaking fluency—relatively higher automaticity compared to coherence and accuracy—reflects a common trend in language development. Learners often prioritize getting their message across initially before focusing on precision, as noted in the analysis. However, the significant disparity between automaticity and accuracy underscores a potential imbalance, which, if unaddressed, could lead to the fossilization of errors, a concern frequently discussed in second language acquisition literature.

The implications of these findings for language instruction resonate with established pedagogical principles. The suggestion to design activities that integrate all three dimensions of fluency simultaneously aligns with communicative language teaching approaches that emphasize holistic skill development. The example of structured speaking tasks requiring specific grammatical structures (accuracy) while organizing ideas logically (coherence) and speaking without excessive pauses (automaticity) offers a practical application of this integrated approach. Furthermore, the call for providing targeted feedback on accuracy without discouraging spontaneous speech highlights the delicate balance that teachers must maintain to foster both fluency and accuracy in their students' spoken English.

In conclusion, the data from this study provides a comprehensive view of the Grade 8 learners' speaking abilities, indicating that while they have developed a degree of

automaticity, they require considerable support in enhancing the coherence and accuracy of their spoken language. By adopting instructional strategies that address these dimensions in an integrated manner, language instructors in Cagayan de Oro can effectively guide their students beyond "Fair Fluency" towards more proficient and well-rounded speaking skills, better preparing them for future academic and professional endeavors.

Research Question 5: Do the participants' level of English language proficiency, speaking confidence, and digital exposure significantly influence their English speaking fluency?

Ho1. The participants' English language proficiency, speaking confidence, and digital exposure do not significantly influence their English speaking fluency.

Ho2. The participants' level of English language proficiency does not significantly influence their speaking fluency.

Ho3. The participants' level of speaking confidence does not significantly influence their speaking fluency.

Ho4. The participants' level of digital exposure does not significantly influence their speaking fluency.

Table 5 presents the regression analysis conducted to examine the influence of English language proficiency specifically vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension, speaking confidence, and digital exposure encompassing interaction with digital media and the use of AI tools on the participants' speaking fluency. Evidently, the analysis reveals that the overall model is statistically significant [$F(3, 241) = 4.86, p = .003$], leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis that these variables, as a set, do not influence speaking fluency. Consequently, this significance indicates that, collectively, English language proficiency, speaking confidence, and digital exposure play a meaningful role in shaping the participants' ability to speak fluently in English.

Table 5
Regression Analysis of the Influence of Participants' Language Proficiency, Speaking Confidence, and Digital Exposure on their Speaking Fluency

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.590	.267		5.955	.000
English Language Proficiency	.042	.015	.172	2.74**	.007
Speaking Confidence	-.064	.065	-.062	-.988	.324
Digital Exposure	.146	.067	.138	2.19*	.029

Model Summary

$R = .239$ $R^2 = .057$ Adjusted $R^2 = .045$ $F(3,241) = 4.86$ $p = .003$

*Legend: ** significant at 0.001 level; * significant at 0.05 level*

Specifically, regarding English language proficiency, the null hypothesis stating that it does not significantly influence speaking fluency was rejected. The analysis revealed a statistically significant positive association ($B = .042$, $p = .007$). This suggests that higher levels of English Language Proficiency are linked to greater speaking fluency. Indeed, this finding is corroborated by research from Rahman and Tomy (2024), whose study with EFL learners also found a positive correlation between language proficiency and their speaking fluency.

However, concerning speaking confidence, the null hypothesis asserting that it does not significantly influence speaking fluency was not rejected ($B = -.064$, $p = .324$). Thus, the analysis did not find a statistically significant relationship between the participants' reported speaking confidence and their speaking fluency. Interestingly, this aligns with the observations of Darasawang and Reinders (2021), who suggested that while confidence might play a role in a learner's willingness to communicate, it does not always directly translate to higher levels of fluency, particularly if foundational language skills are not sufficiently developed.

Furthermore, in terms of digital exposure, the null hypothesis proposing that it does not significantly influence speaking fluency was rejected. The analysis indicated a statistically significant positive impact ($B = .146$, $p = .029$). Therefore, greater engagement with digital resources is associated with higher speaking fluency. This is consistent with the work of Hasumi and Chiu (2024), who highlighted the potential of technology-enhanced language learning to improve speaking skills, and Maurya et al. (2023), whose research linked the use of digital resources to enhanced oral communication abilities.

Despite the significant influences of English Language Proficiency and digital exposure on speaking fluency identified in this analysis, the low R^2 value (.057) for the overall model indicates that these factors account for only a small portion of the total variance. This implies that other unmeasured variables, such as real-life speaking opportunities as noted by Keil et al. (2021) and emotional factors as highlighted by Wang et al. (2024), likely play a more substantial role in the development of speaking fluency.

Conclusions

This study illuminates that among language learners in Cagayan de Oro, Northern Mindanao, Philippines, English language proficiency and digital exposure are significant positive predictors of speaking fluency, highlighting the crucial role of strong foundational language skills and the thoughtful integration of digital resources in the local educational environment to improve oral communication abilities. Notably, the findings indicate that

speaking confidence did not show a statistically significant direct impact on speaking fluency, suggesting that while vital for a learner's willingness to communicate, it may not directly lead to measurable increases in fluency levels. The study also suggests that other unexamined factors likely play a role in speaking fluency, potentially including speaking confidence in more complex ways or other variables such as real-life practice opportunities and learner motivation.

Consequently, these findings imply a need for language education in Cagayan de Oro to prioritize the development of robust language proficiency and strategically leverage digital resources. Educators should adopt a more complex understanding of the relationship between confidence and fluency, recognizing that while important, confidence alone may not be the primary driver of fluency. Further research is warranted to explore the multifaceted nature of speaking fluency development within this specific educational setting, potentially investigating the influence of other contributing factors and the more nuanced ways in which confidence might impact oral communication.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and analysis of this study, several recommendations are put forth to address the identified challenges in fostering students' speaking fluency, language proficiency, confidence, and digital engagement. For language teachers, it is recommended to increase opportunities for spontaneous oral practice through activities like impromptu speaking, role-playing, and peer interviews to enhance automaticity and reduce hesitation. They should also consider integrating grammar and vocabulary instruction within meaningful communicative tasks rather than relying on isolated exercises. Furthermore, teachers are encouraged to strengthen the use of comprehension-based activities to effectively link receptive and productive language skills. Building students' confidence is crucial, and teachers should focus on providing supportive feedback, minimizing judgment during speaking activities, and normalizing errors as a natural part of the learning process. Finally, it is advisable for teachers to introduce students to digital platforms that offer speaking practice, such as language chatbots, pronunciation applications, and AI tutors, while also guiding them on how to use these tools effectively.

For school administrators, it is recommended to prioritize and intensify professional development opportunities for teachers, focusing on communicative teaching strategies, fluency development techniques, and the integration of technology into language instruction. Administrators should also consider improving access to functional digital tools, language learning applications, and reliable internet connectivity to support both classroom-based and independent language practice for students. Moreover, the continuation and encouragement of school-wide programs and clubs that promote English language use in both formal and informal settings, such as English Speaking Month and storytelling contests, are highly recommended.

Finally, for future researchers, several avenues of inquiry are suggested. It would be beneficial to explore additional factors that may influence speaking fluency, including

student motivation, learning strategies employed, family language background, and the frequency of real-life language use. Conducting longitudinal studies could help determine the long-term impact of digital exposure and comprehension-focused teaching methodologies on speaking performance. Further research could also examine the role of anxiety and personality traits in shaping students' willingness to communicate in English.

Lastly, investigating the effectiveness of specific AI tools, digital platforms, and mobile applications in improving real-time speaking fluency among Filipino learners would provide valuable insights for educators and technology developers.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research strictly adhered to ethical standards throughout its conduct. Prior to data collection, approval was formally secured from Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee to ensure the study's procedures aligned with ethical guidelines. Furthermore, informed consent was diligently obtained from both the participating students and their parents or legal guardians, ensuring their voluntary participation and full understanding of the study's purpose and procedures. To safeguard the participants' rights and privacy, all data collected were handled in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 of the Philippines. The study was guided by the key ethical principles outlined in the Belmont Report, namely respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, ensuring that participants were treated with dignity, potential benefits of the research were maximized while minimizing harm, and participation was equitable.

REFERENCES

- Ahn, Y. Y. (2020). *Analysis of Classroom Dynamics in a Teaching Methods Course: An ELF Teacher Educator's Beliefs and Instructional Decisions About Teaching English in South Korea*. Indiana University.
- Alkhadim, G. S. (2022). Cronbach's alpha and semantic overlap between items: A proposed correction and tests of significance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 815490. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.815490>
- Azzam, M. H. (2021). *A Qualitative Phenomenological Study on the Lived Experiences of Dental Hygiene Clinical Instructors on Emotional Intelligence: A Single Case Study* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Bridgeport).
- Bakar, N. A. A., Yunus, M. M., & Ayub, A. F. M. (2021). Speaking anxiety and speaking performance: The correlation between language anxiety and self-confidence. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(1), 57-68.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York: Freeman.
- Biber, D., Conrad, S., & Jones, B. (2020). Using corpus linguistics to analyze university language. In K. Hyland & P. Shaw (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of English for academic purposes* (pp. 23-38). Routledge.
- Bucay, E. R., & Rosil, L. S. (2024). Intrinsic Motivation and Speaking Fluency of Second Language Learners. *International Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, 13(1), 25-36.

- Cagalitan, K. C., Delfin, M. A., & Malicay, J. D. (2023). Perceptions of Teachers toward the Inclusion of Learners with Hearing Impairment in Regular Classrooms. *Online Submission*, 11(6).
- Chen, S., Zang, Y., & Yang, P. (2024). City images in transnational travel vlogs from a multimodal perspective: an investigation of 20 port cities worldwide. *Online Media and Global Communication*, 3(1), 82-107. <https://doi.org/10.29374/OMGC.2024.3.1.5>
- Cheng, Y. S., & Yang, Y. Y. (2019). Language anxiety and speaking performance: From the perspective of expectancy-value theory. *Journal of Language Teaching and Learning*, 9(2), 46-63.
- Darasawang, P., & Reinders, H. (2021). Willingness to communicate and second language proficiency: A correlational study. *Education Sciences*, 11(9), 517. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11090517>
- Dincer, A., & Dariyemez, S. (2020). Foreign language speaking anxiety among EFL learners: The case of preparatory school students. *Journal of Educational Sciences Research*, 10(1), 93-114. <https://doi.org/10.29329/ijer.2020.234.7>
- Dóczy, Z., & Kormos, J. (2021). Vocabulary knowledge and writing performance. *Language Testing*, 38(1), 5-25. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265532219894344>
- Ellis, R. (2020). *Language teaching paradigms revisited*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Ellis, R. (2022). Grammar instruction for language learners. In S. Gass & L. Ortega (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of instructed second language acquisition* (pp. 167-184). Routledge.
- Fabriz, S., Mendzheritskaya, J., & Stehle, S. (2021). Impact of synchronous and asynchronous settings of online teaching and learning in higher education on students' learning experience during COVID-19. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 733554. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.733554>
- Fauzi, U. A., Emzir, E., & Marlina, L. (2021). Cognitive, linguistic, and affective factors influencing speaking fluency of EFL learners. *English Review: Journal of English Education*, 9(2), 337-346. <https://doi.org/10.25134/erjee.v9i2.5025>
- Foster, P., & Skehan, P. (2021). Measuring fluency in second language production. In P. Robinson (Ed.), *The Routledge handbook of second language acquisition* (pp. 285-300). Routledge.
- Gass, S. M., & Selinker, L. (2019). *Second language acquisition: An introductory course*. Routledge.
- Grabe, W. (2021). Reading in a second language: Cognitive and psycholinguistic foundations. In J. I. Lontas (Ed.), *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching*. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0544>
- Grabe, W., & Stoller, F. L. (2022). *Teaching and researching reading*. Routledge.
- Han, Y., Miller, N., & Kang, O. (2020). Relationships between utterance fluency measures and observed ratings of fluency. *Language Testing*, 37(1), 109-132. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0265532218798694>
- Hasumi, T., & Chiu, M. S. (2024). Technology-enhanced language learning in English language education: Performance analysis, core publications, and emerging trends. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2346044. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2024.2346044>
- Hidayat, D. N., Patras, Y. E., & Peter, M. (2020). Exploring factors affecting students' speaking fluency. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning (JELTL)*, 1(1), 46-53. <https://doi.org/10.33365/jeltl.v1i1.13>
- Hyland, K. (2021). *Disciplinary discourses: Social interactions in academic writing*. University of Michigan Press.
- Jansen, D., Elffers, L., & Volman, M. (2022). And then there were three:(re-) distributing educational responsibilities in response to the growing use of shadow education in the

- Netherlands. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 52(5), 615-632.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2022.2066109>
- Kapp, K. M., Valtchanov, D., & Pastore, R. (2020). Enhancing motivation in workplace training with casual games: A twelve month field study of retail employees. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(5), 2263-2284.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09805-z>
- Keil, A., Krishnapriya, P. P., Mitra, A., Jat, M. L., Sidhu, H. S., Krishna, V. V., & Shyamsundar, P. (2021). Changing agricultural stubble burning practices in the Indo-Gangetic plains: is the Happy Seeder a profitable alternative?. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 19(2), 128-151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14735903.2020.1794633>
- Koda, K. (2023). *Second language reading: Cognitive and linguistic perspectives*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lambert, J., & Zhang, Y. J. (2022). Social presence, learning engagement, and learning outcomes in online language courses. *CALICO Journal*, 39(1), 64-84.
<https://doi.org/10.1558/cj.20521>
- Larsen-Freeman, D. (2021). Complexity, accuracy, and fluency in second language production. In J. I. Lontos (Ed.), *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching*. Wiley.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0079>
- Lee, G. M., & Chen, Y. L. (2022). Effects of immersion in virtual reality language learning environments on foreign language fluency and confidence. *Computers & Education*, 186, 104548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104548>
- Lemana II, H. E. (2022). Communication strategies of English majors in Philippine classroom discourses: Basis for an enhancement module on strategic competence. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 2(2), 48-59.
- Lestari, L. A., Emilia, E., & Mydiansyah, M. (2019). Exploring factors affecting students' speaking skill. *The Journal of English Language Teaching*, 8(1), 77-85.
- Loew, C. A., Schauenburg, H., & Dinger, U. (2020). Self-criticism and psychotherapy outcome: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 75, 101808.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2019.101808>
- MacIntyre, P. D., & Gregersen, T. (2021). Language anxiety and speaking confidence in language learning. In Z. Dörnyei & S. Ryan (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of instructed second language acquisition* (pp. 60-79). Routledge.
- Marchiori, W. M. (2023). *English as a Lingua Franca in the European Union*. [Insert Publisher if known].
- Maurya, S., Akhtar, S., & Khan, M. K. A. (2023). Immunoinformatics Approach for the Design of Chimeric Vaccine Against Whitmore Disease. *The Open Bioinformatics Journal*, 16(1).
- McCarthy, M. (2021). *Discourse analysis for language teachers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Montrul, S. A. (2021). *The acquisition of heritage languages*. Cambridge University Press.
- Morales, A. (2021). Effects of strategy instruction on EFL learners' oral fluency development. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 31(1), 99-119.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ijal.12308>
- Mulyani, V., & Wibisono, B. Y. (2021). Utilizing digital platforms to enhance students' speaking skills in EFL classrooms. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning (JELTL)*, 2(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.33365/jeltl.v2i1.1067>
- Muñoz-Ocampo, A. M. (2022). Confidence in speaking English as a foreign language: Voices from Colombian pre-service teachers. *GIST Education and Learning Research Journal*, 34(3), 184-204. <https://doi.org/10.18046/j.gist.2022.34.16>
- Nation, I. S. P. (2020). *Learning vocabulary in another language*. Cambridge University Press.
- Rahman, A., & Tomy, P. (2024). Intelligent personal assistant-an interlocutor to mollify foreign language speaking anxiety. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 32(8), 4569-4586.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2022.2054873>

- Rahman, M. M., Karim, M. R., & Islam, M. S. (2021). Digital technology in ESL classrooms: Impacts on students' language learning. *World Journal of English Language*, 11(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wjel.v11n1p1>
- Ravshanovna, K. L. (2024). Enhancing foreign language education through integration of digital technologies. *Miasto Przyszłości*, (44), 131-138.
- Rincon, G. A., Cezar, R. F., & Hernandez, C. F. (2020). Beliefs about mathematics and academic performance: A descriptive-correlational analysis. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1514, No. 1, p. 012021). IOP Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1514/1/012021>
- Rodrguez-Escobar, C., Cuevas-Lepe, J., & Maluenda-Parraguez, L. (2023). Assessing the effectiveness of Wordwall. net as a vocabulary learning tool: Pre-service EFL teachers' perspectives. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 14(31), 41-51.
- Rost, M. (2020). *Teaching and researching listening*. Routledge.
- Saito, K., & Plonsky, L. (2023). Effects of second language instruction on second language speech fluency development: A meta-analysis. *Applied Linguistics Review*.
- Schmitt, N. (2019). *Vocabulary in language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
- Segalowitz, N. (2022). Reflections on the past and future of research on second language fluency. *The Modern Language Journal*, 106(1), 194-207. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12744>
- Senaratne, H., Oviatt, S., Ellis, K., & Melvin, G. (2022). A critical review of multimodal-multisensor analytics for anxiety assessment. *ACM Transactions on Computing for Healthcare*, 3(4), 1-42. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3534993>
- Vandergrift, L., & Goh, C. C. M. (2019). *Teaching and learning second language listening: Metacognition in action*. Routledge.
- Wang, W., Rezaei, Y. M., & Izadpanah, S. (2024). Speaking accuracy and fluency among EFL learners: The role of creative thinking, emotional intelligence, and academic enthusiasm. *Heliyon*, 10(18).
- Zhang, X., Lewis, S., Firth, J., Chen, X., & Bucci, S. (2021). Digital mental health in China: a systematic review. *Psychological medicine*, 51(15), 2552-2570.